

Impact assessment as a conversation

*Transforming student expectations into proposals
for future editions of the Internet Festival.*

*This article describes the **audience data collection and analysis** activities conducted as part of the Data Conversations project by Fondazione Sistema Toscana (FST), the project coordinator, and the University of Florence, the project partner. The aim is to inspire other cultural organisations organising events to assess their impact.*

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Context and purpose

Internet Festival as a case study for impact analysis activities

Internet Festival - Forme di Futuro is an annual event organised by Fondazione Sistema Toscana, held every October in Pisa and dedicated to exploring and disseminating digital technology and culture. The Tutorial Tours (T-Tours) are the educational heart of the festival.

These learning and training pathways are designed specifically for schools and teachers, and aim to stimulate curiosity and provide tools for navigating the world of digital innovation through labs, workshops, educational games, and interactive installations. The T-Tours provided the context in which the Data Conversations consortium tested various impact assessment techniques.

The impact assessment objective within the T-Tours

Impact assessment requires significant organizational effort; however, it offers insights and answers that help deliver better activities to the audience, both in terms of content and delivery methods.

An initiative like the T-Tours can not be limited to the collection and measurement of purely quantitative indicators (such as the number of participants or hours delivered), but must include a qualitative analysis capable of capturing the change and transformation they trigger.

Investigating the impact generated offers three benefits:

1. Going beyond a simple attendance count helps organisers to understand if the event led to an actual increase in knowledge (**outcome**);
2. Providing stakeholders with concrete data regarding the return on investment of the resources used (financial, human, and time) legitimises the continuation of the project itself (**accountability**);
3. Enabling the identification of program strengths and gaps informs improvement in both content and format (**continuous improvement**).

The 2025 edition of the T-Tours **involved students in a two-stage data collection process**: the first was conducted a couple of weeks before the event to understand the expectations of the young audience; the second focused on gathering students' immediate impressions following the activities, with the more traditional goal of measuring overall satisfaction. As a primary result, this activity allowed for the collection of **feedback directly from the T-Tours' end-users**, without it being filtered through the teachers' evaluations.

This article focuses on the pre-event data collection process. We will describe our **goals**, the **methodology** used, the **type of analysis** performed, and the **future applications** of the findings.

Expectation mapping: gathering data before the festival

The pre-festival data collection (*ex-ante analysis*) was conducted to establish a baseline for subsequent **impact assessment** phases and, specifically, to understand the **cognitive and emotional expectations** of the students registered for the T-Tour activities. This exercise served as a tool to evaluate the **alignment** between the planned programming and the actual interests expressed by the audience. The objective was to provide an information base for future editions of the event, ensuring that the festival's content, themes, and delivery methods **respond effectively to the needs of the younger audience**, while accounting for the constant and rapid evolution of the digital world and its related expectations.

Teachers were asked to collect written responses from their students to the open-ended question: **"What would you like to find at the Internet Festival?"** The question was intentionally kept broad to allow students to interpret it freely, with the only recommendation being to keep their answers brief.

Teachers were expressly requested **not to intervene in the response process**: neither by guiding students during the writing phase, nor by correcting or filtering the answers before sending them to the festival team.

In cases where teachers intervened by providing specific details about the upcoming festival activities, the resulting responses were overly focused on specific themes. This created a **bias** that partially restricted the students' ability to freely express their broader expectations regarding the digital world¹.

We gathered nearly **400 responses** from students in primary schools (6-11 y.o.), middle schools (11-14 y.o.), and high schools (14-19 y.o.). The tone of the feedback was quite diverse, ranging from highly specific requests (*"I want to see a practical demonstration of AI in video games, a boss that adapts to the player, or a map generated based on player input using models from a folder"* – high school student) to more general indications focused on current trends (*"I would like to find a plan on how AI will be used across all sectors in the future and the new professions that might emerge"* – high school student).

Suggestions emerged regarding both the content and the format of the events. For instance, one student expressed the desire for *"... a workshop with a mini robot... that tells you the ecological footprint of an object you show it"* (middle school student). Another suggested *"... trying out some games or tools to learn things while having fun"* (high school student).

Feedback also included more lighthearted and 'atmospheric' comments, like one student's wish to *"...find stands, stalls, chaos, and a lot of fun"* (primary school student).

¹ In one specific case, a teacher rephrased the original question into a highly specific query: **"What do you expect from the workshop A Classic Future: Stories and Images?"**. As a result, the responses focused solely on the elements mentioned in the title itself. Although the research scope had been predefined, we chose not to discard these findings as they still held informative value. Despite their lower statistical significance, these data provided insights into students' expectations regarding the relationship between storytelling and imagery.

Most responses were submitted **via email**, except for one class that provided their feedback in person as paper copies. While the educational level was indicated at the time of submission, we do not have data concerning the gender of the participants.

Data analysis

Interpreting open-ended answers - typical of qualitative methodology - involves analysing **unstructured data** (text, words) to understand the **opinions, motivations, and emotions** of respondents. This process captures nuances that enrich the overall understanding, **going beyond simple dichotomous (yes/no) answers**.

In the case of the Internet Festival data collection, this required rigorous coding methods to manage subjectivity and extract valid insights from the more than **40,000 characters of responses received**. The festival team decided to proceed along two distinct lines of action.

The first, a traditional approach, involved an **in-depth reading of the responses** to understand the needs of the young audience. This analysis allowed for the identification of **recurring themes**, reflection on the types of requests based on the school level, and an assessment of the extent to which the 2025 edition was **already prepared to meet those expectations**.

The second line of analysis, described in the following sections, involved a collaboration between the festival team and the **Department of Industrial Engineering** at the **University of Florence (UniFi)**, a partner – alongside FST – in the Data Conversations project. UniFi provided its specialized expertise in **text mining** and **Natural Language Processing (NLP)**, adapting these techniques to the specific context of a cultural organization like the festival.

The first step was to initiate a **conversation** between the two teams, each expert in different domains, to define potential areas for collaboration and modes of interaction. **Collaboration** is crucial for understanding each other's fields of knowledge and how their respective skills can complement one another. **Interaction** is equally important to define the specific tasks of each team, ensuring that activities are integrated effectively.

Topic modeling and interpretation of the topics

The students' responses were analysed by UniFi using *Topic Modeling*, an automated analysis technique capable of identifying the **most relevant subjects**. Its main steps are summarised below. For a more detailed technical overview, please refer to Annex 1.

Topic modeling by UniFi

Text preparation: the data was "cleaned" by converting everything to lowercase and removing punctuation and common, low-significance words such as articles and prepositions (stop words).

Word Simplification (**Lemmatization**): each word was reduced to its base form (for example, "would like" or "wanting" were reduced to the root form "want").

Word counting: a table was created to count how many times each simplified word appears in every individual response.

Topic identification: using a statistical model called Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), **7 main latent topics** were identified. Each of the 7 topics represents a specific subject, consisting of a group of words that tend to co-occur in the texts. The 10 most representative words for each topic were extracted and visualised in a chart (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Top 10 terms per topic

To further investigate the expectations of the three educational levels (primary, middle, and high schools) that participated in the survey, **potential differences between these subgroups were explored**. Additionally, targeted textual analyses were performed on the open-ended responses of each of the three groups.

Textual description by the festival team

Once the main topic model was defined - with each topic representing a coherent set of frequently associated words - two members of the festival team worked on a **textual description** for each group. An interpretive approach was used: much like connecting the stars of a constellation in the night sky, the team linked the elements of each topic, **transforming the data into a logical and descriptive narrative** that could be utilised by the rest of the staff.

Faced with the themes extracted by the statistical system, the team initially experienced a sense of **uncertainty**, fearing that the apparent "objectivity" of those cold, statistically-derived data points might lose the deeper meaning of the content. Only a complete reading of the responses (what we previously called an "in-depth reading") allowed us to bridge this gap and find a **compromise between automated calculation and domain**

expertise. This process of fusion was necessary to breathe meaning into words that, when decontextualised, risked remaining nothing more than **cold data sequences.**

Familiarity with the context and **target audience** of the T-Tours, combined with the insight gained from the preliminary reading, made it possible to **give shape to the students' requests.** This allowed the team to link them to the festival's formats and themes, assign **different weights to the requests,** and identify **potential trends or biases.**

General results

Below, we present the results of the textual description for the 7 topics, which was developed independently of the participants' school cycles. Please note that the chart accompanying each analysis displays only the top 10 occurrences, whereas the actual analysis was conducted on a larger set of words comprising each topic. Each description is accompanied by a detailed visualisation of the top 10 terms for each topic model.

AI and New Technologies

Students demonstrate a strong interest in projects related to Artificial Intelligence. Rather than seeking superficial knowledge, they aim for an in-depth understanding that allows them to learn how new technologies actually work. Learning must be stimulated through activities that combine study, practice, and a playful dimension, ensuring the process is both engaging and effective.

Interact to Learn

Students wish to engage with practical and interactive activities, such as workshops, exhibitions, or games. They seek a stimulating learning experience that sparks enjoyment and curiosity, offering the opportunity to interact directly with technology through a straightforward exchange and dialogue between teachers and learners.

Developing Skills

Students are eager to participate in activities related to the world of video games. Their interest goes beyond mere entertainment, extending to an understanding of the technologies that make them possible. They seek the opportunity to engage in "hands-on" creation to develop practical and valuable skills.

Experimenting to Learn

Students wish to take part in engaging experiences, including those related to 3D printing technology. For them, direct experimentation is the most effective way to learn. At the same time, they expect to meet experts who can make the activities fun and involve them actively.

Immersive Technologies and Virtual Worlds

Students wish to engage in immersive experiences that include the use of VR headsets and to try simulators, gaming environments, and video games. Their interest goes beyond mere passive use: they want to explore the potential of AI and understand how programming enables the creation of virtual worlds. They seek to understand the underlying mechanics in order to contribute to the development of new technologies.

Robotics and Active Learning

Students want to engage in active learning experiences within the world of robotics, including exploring the relationship between humans and machines. They seek a fun and accessible approach that allows them to get closer to the mechanics of programming in a natural and engaging way.

The Impact of Technology

Students wish to delve into various technological fields, such as virtual reality and robotics. A recurring theme is the request for learning methods that differ from traditional school-based approaches. There is a strong curiosity to understand both the positive and negative impacts that digital technology exerts on society.

Results by school level

Below, we present the results of the textual description of the topics emerging from the comparison between the three school levels.

Primary schools

Figure 2: Primary school topics

Curiosity and Experiential Fun

Primary school students call for experiences based on play and fun. They desire activities capable of simulating immersive physical realities and expect to interact with technology in a playful way, using devices that particularly fascinate them, such as smartphones, tablets, and computers.

Technological Content and Themes

They want the festival to respond interactively to their learning needs, including in relation to school subjects. Their interests range from video games and robotics to the world of sports.

Contextual Expectations

They look for activities where fun - even of a spontaneous nature- is at the heart of the experience. Furthermore, the presence of a food corner is considered essential to making the experience feel complete and welcoming.

Middle schools

Figure 3: Middle school topics

Learning, Technologies, and Interaction

Middle school students seek educational activities that combine fun and engagement. Participation should take a game-based form to foster active learning through direct experiences where participants can play an active, hands-on role.

Technological Content and Themes

Interest is primarily focused on robotics - specifically the relationship between robots and humans - and Artificial Intelligence. They want to explore virtual reality, including through the use of VR headsets. Video games are viewed both as entertainment tools and as objects to be designed and programmed. Finally, they wish to experiment with tools such as 3D printers.

Contextual Expectations

The specific request for the food corner suggests that expectations also extend to the festival's physical environment and ancillary services (such as food availability), aiming for an overall experience that integrates technology, comfort, and social interaction.

High schools

Figure 4: High school topics

Technology, Future, and Practice

High school students wish to engage directly and visually with technological innovations, innovative hardware, and cutting-edge devices. They seek active learning oriented toward experimentation and creation, through full immersion in exhibitions and hands-on, interactive workshops that go beyond mere passive observation.

Their interest includes the development of concrete skills, such as programming and the use of advanced technological tools.

Technological Content and Themes

They demonstrate an awareness of global digital trends and a desire to understand their impact. Artificial Intelligence is a central theme, both as an innovation to explore and as a practical tool to utilise. Their interest in cybersecurity highlights the need to understand technology within the contexts of security and risk management. They seek experiences that show how technology can address future challenges, favoring activities focused on innovation and long-term impact.

In particular, they show a strong interest in robotics, moving beyond theory to the opportunity to observe and understand how robots actually function. They demand high-engagement experiences, such as the use of 3D headsets and the exploration of virtual environments through simulators or video games. Furthermore, they are curious about technical deep dives into tools like digital archives, data management, and advanced IT systems.

Reflecting on the "Absences"

The team's data fluency enabled a focused analysis of the **absences** – a key consideration for those organising an innovation-focused event. In this context, absences refer to digital themes and aspects that were not requested by participants. This silence is significant and can stem from different roots: it may indicate a lack of interest, either because the topic

lacks appeal or because users believe there is nothing new to add to what they already know; alternatively, it may signal a lack of awareness, where users simply cannot request what they do not know exists. Since people tend to desire what they already know, what is missing from the responses is just as crucial as what appears. Ultimately, these answers reveal the 'knowledge bubble' in which people operate, highlighting how an innovation event must strive to burst that bubble and offer new territories to explore. People tend to desire what they already know; therefore, what is missing from the responses is just as crucial as what appears.

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Use and target audience for the results

How will the Internet Festival use data analysis?

It is important to note that the results (all kinds of results, both coming from pre-event and post-event assessment) will be discussed and applied across various contexts, based on the specific expertise of the different stakeholders. In the case of the festival, the stakeholders are:

- **Honorary Committee**, composed of the political representatives of the event. This body will be able to refine their understanding of the event's audience and evaluate how well the public's needs align with the core nature of the festival.
- **Executive Committee**, which defines the festival's macro-actions each year and will thus be able to identify the macro-themes for future proposals.
- **Production Staff**, who practically organise the individual activities and will thus be able to encourage workshop proposals that align with the identified aspirations and address any potential gaps.

The data collected is not intended solely for the festival organisers. There are other fundamental target audiences: namely the **teachers** and **students** whose contributions made it possible to carry out this analytical work.

Teachers can use the information collected to better understand their classes' expectations and potentially integrate them into their internal school activities.

The students are the ones who provided the data; they will be able to verify whether their feelings and expectations have been correctly interpreted and potentially provide further insights.

Conclusions

The impact assessment conducted on Internet Festival's T-Tours has demonstrated the strategic value of interdisciplinary collaboration. Merging the technical expertise of the Department of Industrial Engineering at the University of Florence with the Festival team's deep understanding of the cultural context and target audience has generated results that would have been difficult to achieve through a single-perspective approach. This partnership did not stop at providing tools; it also opened a horizon of potential future paths, with a view toward the reproducibility of the work performed.

The entire process was structured as a **conversation**: on one hand, a dialogue between scientific and cultural expertise; on the other, a conversation between the diverse perspectives and sensibilities of the festival's own team members. In this sense, the analysis was not a mere technical synthesis, but an interpretive act, capable of transforming data into shared knowledge.

To be meaningful, data analysis must therefore be a **shared, multi-perspective** process rather than a top-down model. The analysis is the result of **continuous refinement** and reworking to achieve a common goal. Technology provides tools that only human interpretation can and must validate, in search of directions capable of guiding the festival's future decisions.

Annex 1

Data Preparation and Cleaning

The open-ended responses collected during the pre-event survey phase were initially imported in electronic format (Excel file) and subjected to a text normalization process.

All text was converted to lowercase to ensure uniformity and consistency in the analysis. Furthermore, punctuation marks, extra spaces, and stopwords - frequent Italian terms with no significant informational content (such as articles, prepositions, and conjunctions like “il,” “di,” “e,” “che”) - were removed.

This cleaning phase made it possible to reduce noise in the data and focus the analysis on the most significant semantic elements.

Linguistic Lemmatization

The text corpus was subsequently lemmatized using the **UDPipe linguistic model** for the Italian language (**italian-isdt-ud-2.5**).

Lemmatization allowed for the reduction of various inflected word forms to their base form (lemma), making semantically equivalent terms comparable and aggregatable, for example: “vorrei” (I wish), “vorremmo” (we wish), and “volere” (to wish) → “volere” (to wish).

This step contributed to improving the overall quality of the analysis by limiting the artificial fragmentation of lexical frequencies.

Construction of the Document-Term Matrix (DTM)

Based on the lemmatized text, a **Document-Term Matrix (DTM)** was constructed to serve as the quantitative foundation for the analysis. Within the matrix:

- The **rows** correspond to individual responses from the students;
- The **columns** represent the lemmas identified within the corpus;
- The **cells** indicate the frequency with which each lemma appears in each response.

The DTM enabled the systematic application of statistical **topic modeling** techniques.

Analysis strategy: general and school-level models

The topic modeling analysis was structured across multiple levels to capture both cross-cutting expectations and specificities related to different school levels.

In the first phase, a general **topic modeling model** was constructed and applied to the entire corpus of responses, regardless of the school level. This model allowed for the identification of the primary themes shared by the T-Tour audience as a whole.

Subsequently, **three distinct topic modeling models** were estimated, each referring to a specific school level:

- Primary school;
- Middle school;
- High school.

This second phase made it possible to explore **specific thematic differences and recurrences by school group**, highlighting differentiated expectations, interests, and languages based on age and educational background.

Selecting the optimal number of topics

For each model, the **Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA)** method was applied, testing a variable number of topics ranging from 2 to 10.

For each value of k , the **perplexity** was calculated and used as an indicator of model quality (lower values indicate a better ability to represent the data). For each model, the number of topics that minimized the perplexity was selected as the optimal solution.

Construction and interpretation of LDA models

Once the optimal parameters were defined, the final LDA models were estimated. Each topic can be interpreted as a coherent set of words that tend to appear together in the responses, indicating a recurring theme in the expectations expressed by the students.

For each topic, **the 10 most representative terms** were extracted—specifically those with the highest probability of belonging to that topic (β).

The results were visualized through bar charts and subsequently subjected to a qualitative interpretive analysis by the festival team, in relation to the event's context and objectives.